

Tourists' Decision Making in Choosing Destination Place

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Abstract: Recently, the tourism industry is one of the largest industries and a services sector with the most rapid growth rates in the world. The purpose of this research is to understand what factors determine tourists when choosing a tourist destination in Lembang, Bandung. Qualitative methodology was chosen and analyzed with case study. In this research, a destination place which becomes popular rapidly selected as a case study because many photos that taking in that destination going viral. The data is collected by conducted interviews with tourist that visiting an attractive destination in Lembang. In order to decrease the data bias, interview was conducted in that destination. The findings in this research, current tourists, especially tourists who visit Bandung, prefer a destination place that can provide uniqueness which is they can not acquired in other destinations. Uniqueness will help them to get interesting photos for their next upload on their own social media.

KEYWORDS: destination; tourism; Bandung; Decision Making

1. INTRODUCTION

Recently, the tourism industry is one of the largest industries and a services sector with the most rapid growth rates in the world. Along with technology and information industry, the tourism industry is expected to become prime movers of economy 21st century. Through the internet a destination can become viral and attract the attention of tourists. In Bandung, some destination place becomes popular in social media.

One destination that becomes popular rapidly in the internet is "European Village" in Lembang, Bandung. According detik.com, this destinations become popular because it is considered one of the destinations that instagenic. Instagenic itself means place which produce gorgeous photos for upload on instagram as background. Destination that instagenic can provide their visitor to take more selfie.

European Village offers several spots by beautiful scenery to take pictures like European-style home, gardens, artificial waterfalls, padlock of love, and the most famous one is the view of the "European House". The spot is unique because it has a view like a house in the popular Hollywood movie with the surrounding scenery in Europe titled "The Lord of The Rings". In addition to the European House, visitors can feed and take pictures with various animals such as rabbits, goats, and sheep. Tourists can also take pictures while putting on traditional European costumes and buy typical of Europe and Indonesia handicrafts.

The advantages of a destination place is influenced by the quality of the object concerned both the quality of the material and the quality of support services. Through the quality of service provided to visitors, is expected that visitors will feel satisfied after a visit. Satisfaction of visitors is expected to be a motivation to make the next visit or invite people nearby to visit attractions that have been previously visited.

The decision of the tourists to visit is not only based on information obtained from the promotion, but also influenced by the consumer's knowledge about the quality of service in the destination place. Quality of service can create a good image or bad image of a tourist attraction, because basically offered a tourist attraction is a service or service to be provided. The existence of customer satisfaction about the services it receives will affect consumer desire to make further purchases (Eboli, 2007)

Kotler and Armstrong (2001) states that purchasing decisions are the stage in the decision making process where the consumer is actually buying. Destination place is a service product offered by a service company with the intention that consumers come to visit and enjoy the attractions offered.

According to Tjiptono (2004) facilities are physical resources that must exist before services are offered to consumers. Basically the facility in the service company is a factor that determines the choice of people to visit the destination place. Many service companies perceive that the interaction of customers with service facilities affect the services in the eyes of customers.

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Ease of using the facility becomes an important thing for consumers to make purchasing decisions. Facilities in destination place and in accordance with the trends that consumers are interested in will be an attraction for consumers to visit and enjoy the facility, not only that cleanliness, fluency and security of the facility is also a plus to attract consumers to visit. Variations of many destination place is determined by the attraction contained in the destination place to be visited, whether in accordance with the wishes of tourists. Tourists will be interested to visit a tourist attraction by looking at what is offered or provided by a destination place.

A destination place can provide a variety of different facilities to tourists. A destination place should be able to choose the most suitable facilities in order to become a popular destination. Along with the existence of some destination place in Bandung that became popular rapidly, then this research aims to understand what factors determine tourists decision making when choosing a tourist destination in Bandung.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

It important for companies to adapted new communication channels, trends and integrate online networks into their online communication strategy. By taking part in different online communities, in that case from social media that consumers sharing their experiences through testimonials, pictures and videos, companies could communicate in more effective way as a well as better manage what it is said about them on the internet. Additionally and since the coming of internet the social media never stopped gaining in importance leading to a new communication paradigm (Mangold and Faulds, 2009). Within online communication greatly increased forcing companies to take them into consideration and integrate a new dimension into their online communication strategy. By integrating this dimension into their online communication strategy, companies open up new interesting opportunities as well as then manage and control it.

According to Prof. Moratti (Yoeti, 1996), tourism destinations must have three essential elements, namely:

1. Must have 'something to see', where it should be an object and a special tourist attraction, which is different to those of other regions to be seen.
2. Must provide 'something to do', namely in that place should be provided facilities for doing recreational activities that can make tourists feel convenience.
3. Must provide 'something to buy', where it should be provided facilities for shopping, especially crafts items that can be brought back to their original places by tourists. If a traveler gain experience both in the third case, then the tourists will spread positive word-of-mouth to family, friends and the surrounding environment or can even spread of electronic word-of-mouth in a way to upload photos or publish the opinion of her experiences through social media. Experience is formed from a tourist and another can be very different depending on the processes that occur in these three elements. A tourist could have missed one of the elements, for example, a traveler chooses to not purchase handicrafts at these destinations. So the experience of a tourist who buy and do not buy will be very different.

Nowadays, people are always taking photos anywhere, from the food they eat to the places they visit. No exception to the tourists. The tourists will immortalize their visit through the photos and then upload them to social media to show where they have been.

As previously, since electronic word-of-mouth proved to be crucial of influence regarding the consumers making decision to purchase a product or service (Simonson and Rosen, 2014), it is decisive for a company to stimulate it and obviously make sure that consumers spread positive comments related to the brand. In tourism industry, often being major source of travel information for consumers, electronic word-of-mouth thus play a decisive role into the consumer final decision (Pantano and Di Pietro, 2013). According to Lewis and Chamber (2000) tourism product are perceived as very risky purchases for which the emotional risk of reference group assessment is a significant element in reaching a final decision (Litvin et al., 2008). The decision making process itself has five stages (Kotler and Keller, 2012) were (1) problem recognition, (2) information search, (3) evaluation alternative (4) purchase, (5) post-purchase.

The first stage is problem recognition. This stage is condition when consumer becomes aware that they need something, in this case, consumer became aware that they need a destination to spend their holiday from daily activities. Second one is information search, the consumer begin to search some information about destination that they need. Consumers are preferred to use information about their destinations through electronic word-of-mouth. Usually they search the destination based on price, location, and kind of type destination like beach or mountain or only looking for some culinary destination. The next stage is evaluation alternative, this is condition when consumer has all the information that they need. After they gathered the information, they compare the information to get the best choice for their destination, like the consumer need beach destination with low price and easy transportation. Purchase. This stage is condition that consumer already decide what kind of

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destination that they want. After the consumer go to the destination, they get some experience from that place. Are they satisfied or they don't want to go back to that place. Negative electronic word-of-mouth is reported to have a huge impact on the image of a destination, as dissatisfied tourists can spread unfavorable remarks regarding their experiences (Litvin et al., 2008). In the era of enhanced internet, more travelers are reported to rely on the internet for transactions and information of their future destinations.

According to Hawkins and Mothersbaugh (2013: 490) on purchasing decisions there are three different types according to the lowest level of engagement to the highest involvement. The three types are through the five stages proposed by Kotler and Keller, but with slight differences in each type.

1. Nominal decision making

In this type, consumers no longer undergo alternative evaluation. Consumers have believed in certain destination place and will not even consider replacing them with other place even though others are cheaper or have other advantages.

2. Limited decision making

Consumers of this type will undergo alternative evaluation stage but with limited alternatives. When a consumer want to visit a destination based on the cheapest price so that the consumer will not care about the view or other advantages. If that destination place change the ticket price and no longer be the cheapest, then consumers will switch to visit another destination that have the cheapest price.

3. Extended decision making

This type is the type which place with many considerations. Similar to the purchase of chocolate bars, consumers on this type will choose based on the cheapest price, the destination place is reliable place or not, the view of the destination, photos spot, even available of restaurant or praying place.

3. METHODOLOGY

This research aims to describe how tourists' destination place in Bandung considered in tourists' decision making in choosing destinations used qualitative methods. A qualitative approach more precisely targets the why and how (Kumar, 2011). The data collection was conducted by interviewing the 13 interviewers who all were visitors the attractive destination in Lembang that has been selected. That destination elected as a case study because this destination was discussed in social media. In case study approach, researchers can select on single case or multiple case study (Brotherton, 2008).

3.1 Research Design

Qualitative chosen because it fits the purpose of this research. Qualitative method is used as the research design to capture the nature of exploratory study which is "form of words" in open question (Creswell, 2003). Because this research purpose is describe how destinations become electronic word-of-mouth and determining consideration to choose destinations, the variables are unknown. Variables will be known from interviews conducted.

The overall research process developed in this report is based on the work of Yin (2003), who divided it into six steps namely:

1. The formulation of the research question.

At this stage is made according to the research question occurring phenomenon clearly.

2. The selection of the cases to study as well as the data gathering approach and analysis method used.

After knowing the research question, then composed how that could represent this study to be a case study, and how the data collected will be conducted.

3. The preparation before collecting data.

Before collecting data, it is necessary to determine the topic of the preparation of such questions that will be made during the interview.

4. The field data collection.

5. The evaluation and analysis of data collected.

After collecting the data according to the needs, then do the analysis based on the data.

6. The conclusions of the study.

Based on the analysis of these data it can be concluded for this study.

The target population in this study was visitors of the attractive destination in Lembang that has been selected. In this study used primary data obtained from interviews. The interview last for about 20 minutes each.

The number of destinations in Bandung was becoming the talk of tourism, one of them was chosen purposefully as a case study. One attractive destination in Lembang selected as a case study. The data collection conducted using the interview method.

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Interviews consisted with some questions about the reasons why visitors chose that destination as the intended destination, how they obtain the information about destination, and whether they would recommend that destination to others. Interview was conducted by semi-structured with open questions. This was done in order to obtain in-depth understanding of the interviewees. In order to interviews can be trusted, rigorous and accountable, then used seven strategies for combating threat to validity expressed by Joseph Maxwell (2009).

Figure 1. Seven strategies for combating threat to validity

Interview conducted repeatedly with detailed and varied data. Similar questions will be asked several times to see whether interviewee gave the same answer. According Robert K. Yin (2011), the practice can be more pervasive and recognized easily which can improve the assumptions made to be more methodic orientation.

3.2 Sampling Technique

In this research, nonprobability sampling is selected. The researcher straight forward to go to one attractive destination in Lembang that has been selected. The interviews conduct with tourist that already visiting that destination to get in-depth interview. In-depth interviews are used in qualitative research so as to not only disclose and understand what and how conditions, but also to stress the why (Saunders *et al.*, 2003). This kind of method has selected in order to get an in-depth understanding of interviewees' perspectives. The In-depth interviews interview gives the interviewer an opportunity to query the interviewees' responses, which may head the discussion into areas which had not been previously been thought of (Saunders *et al.*, 2003).

In order to get in-depth interviews, purposive sampling is the best option, so the interviews could be conducted with tourists that needed to be asked base on our purpose. The purposive sampling signifies that one sees sampling as a series of strategic choices about whom, where, and how one does one's research (Palys, 2008). The researcher decide to go to that destination itself because want to decrease the data bias. The interview conducted with 13 interviewees consist nine female and four male.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on interview that conducted with 13 respondents, this is the results that get by elaborate from 13 interviews. Most of interviewees are female with age about 18 until 35 years old. Most of them are college student that who study around Bandung and were on vacation with their friends. Meanwhile there are also interviewees that vacationing with family.

4.1 The Uniqueness Of The Destination

All interviewee said that the main factor that brings they come to this destination place is the uniqueness. Interviewees said that this destination have many spot that instagenic. Instagenic means all photos take in that spot always beautiful and worth upload in instagram. Besides producing instagenic photos, this destination place also provide unique scenery, that European village in Bandung. The destination that already selected in Lembang has all three essential elements mentioned by Prof. Moratti (Yoeti, 1996).

1. Must have 'something to see'.

That destination place has a spot which are unique to that destination. The spot known as the "European House". Pictures with the background of that spot which attracted many of the tourists that makes many people want to take pictures at that spot. All interviewee stated that they want to take pictures on the spot. Even one of the respondents stated that his second visit to this destination just to take photos at that spot because in first visit, that photo is not good.

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2. Must provide 'something to do'.

That destination that selected offers a pleasant and comfortable destination with beautiful view. According to interviewee, that destination would be the ideal destination for refreshing. Most of interviewee said that this was not too special destination also stated that destination is a pleasant destination to eliminate stress.

3. Must provide 'something to buy'.

In addition to providing a variety of spots to take pictures, that destination also offers a variety of handicrafts as souvenirs. In addition there are also cafes and restaurants for tourists. Half of the interviewee who had bought at the café on the destination stating that the food offered are quite tasty. However, there some interviewee stated that the price is too expensive.

Of the three essential elements, the first element is very influential in the creation of electronic word-of-mouth about that destination. Most of interviewee stated that they are curious about the spot called "European House". The Spot is unique because it has a view like a house in the popular Hollywood movie titled "The Lord of The Rings" with the surrounding scenery in Europe. From a photograph uploaded using that spot as background, gave rise to the interest. Most of interviewee stated they wondered, if these spot as beautiful with the most photos.

After their visit to that destination, some of the interviewees said these destinations beyond their expectations. They say that these destination very nice and there are plenty of spots to take pictures. The rest of the respondents said that the destination is mediocre. However, all respondents stated that they would recommend this destination to other friends, even though they are not completely satisfied with the visit to these destinations but it was enough because they think such a delight as a tourism destination and it did not disappoint.

4.2 Decision Making Process

Almost all respondents said that the main purpose of going to that destination is for refreshing. There is only one respondent who said that the respondents were given the task from schools which should make observations on any of the tourist destinations in Bandung. Then the respondent and friends chose that destination as a destination for observation. In addition to the respondents stated that they want to eliminate the stress of their jobs. College students want to travel after the run midterms, and employees want refreshing of the many office tasks. The reasons given by the interviewee are entering the first stage of the decision making process, namely the problem of recognition. Which is the interviewee became aware that they feel the stress of their jobs or after their midterms, or they have to make observations as a task.

The needs to refreshing encourage someone to seek tourism destinations. Based on these needs, they find the information they need through social media, namely instagram. On instagram they seek destinations that suit their needs. Most of interviewee said that they seek information in instagram by hashtag (#). Interviewees can type hashtag follow with name of the destination place. The number of photos on instagram will be evaluating diverse. The information search process included a second stage in the decision making process, namely information search. Which is the interviewee searching for photos related to the destination places that they want through hashtags on instagram.

All respondents said that they ultimately decided to choose that destination as the intended destination is because the entry ticket price is cheap, the location is easy to find, and moreover that destination is being widely discussed in social media. A lot of photos with scenery background of that destination popping in instagram. Before they decide to come to that destination place, where it enters the fourth stage namely purchase, they through the third stage namely evaluation alternative. Which is the interviewee chose that destination place based on cheap price, the location easy to find, and a lot of photos in instagram.

And the last stage namely post-purchase, this stage occurs after interviewees visiting the destination place. This stage depends on the experience felt by the interviewees, whether they are satisfied or not. Most of the interviewee said that they were satisfied had visited destinations. All interviewee said they would upload their photos while in these destinations to instagram or other social media that they have.

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Figure 2. Decision making in choosing destination place (adapted from Kotler and Keller 2012)

According to Hermawan and Mandasari (2018), Tourists will upload photos taken during their vacation at a destination, if they feel satisfied when visiting that destination. As explained by Hermawan and Mandasari (2018), the photo will be seen by friends and people around them, which will later create an information circle and help a tourist to decide about the destination they will choose.

Figure 3. Decision Making in Circle of Information (adapted from Hermawan and Mandasari, 2018)

Based on the circle of information proposed by Hermawan and Mandasari (2018), it can be seen from the circle that the decision-making process is in it and one that stimulates the search for information about the destination is from friends.

5. CONCLUSION

The aims of this research is to understand what factors determine tourists decision making when choosing a tourist destination in Bandung. The ease of internet access today and the abundance of available social media helps tourists to find information about destinations whenever they want to vacation. Tourists who seek information through social media will be more interested if the place of the destination shows many interesting photos or instagenic photos. Photos that can be categorized as instagenic need a unique place as the background. It can be concluded that the current tourists, especially tourists who visit Bandung, prefer a destination place that can provide uniqueness which is they can not acquired in other destinations. Uniqueness will help them to get interesting photos for their next upload on their own social media.

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